

THE STRUGGLE FOR WOMEN'S RIGHTS

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Abstract: This article provides a brief overview of women's rights. A brief history of the protection of women's rights and the work being done in Uzbekistan in this area.

Key word: Charter of the United Nations, mandate of the General Assembly, Human Rights, WOMEN'S RIGHTS ARE HUMAN RIGHTS, Year of Women, state affairs, the electoral process, healthcare, education, science, culture, labor and social protection.

Since the founding of the United Nations, equality between men and women has been among the most fundamental guarantees of human rights. Adopted in 1945, the Charter of the United Nations sets out as one of its goals "to reaffirm faith in fundamental human rights, in the dignity and worth of the human person, [and] in the equal rights of men and women". Furthermore, Article 1 of the Charter stipulates that one of the purposes of the United Nations is to promote respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms "without distinction as to race, sex, language or religion". This prohibition of discrimination based on sex is repeated in its Articles 13 (mandate of the General Assembly) and 55 (promotion of universal human rights). In 1948, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights was adopted. It, too, proclaimed the equal entitlements of women and men to the rights contained in it, "without distinction of any kind, such as ... sex, ..." In drafting the Declaration, there was considerable discussion about the use of the term "all men" rather than a gender-neutral term.¹ The Declaration was eventually adopted using the terms "all human beings" and "everyone" in order to leave no doubt that the Universal Declaration was intended for everyone, men and women alike.

The struggle for women's rights has always been a hot topic. At all times, women have fought for their rights. Women have been fighting for their rights since the time of the ancient Greek state, and later during the time of the ancient Roman Empire. Women were excluded from voting in ancient Greece and republican Rome, as well as in the few democracies that had emerged in Europe by the end of the 18th century.

Also, after the independence of our country, women's rights were equally ensured in our country and a number of laws were adopted. However, the year 1999 was declared the Year of Women.

Today, large-scale work is being carried out in our country to ensure the rights and legitimate interests of women and girls, the realization of their abilities and opportunities, in a word, the transformation of our sisters into equal, active and creative members of society. All ministries and departments of our republic are widely involved in eliminating women's problems, protecting their rights and increasing their prestige in the family and society, today all organizations and their leaders look at women's problems with different eyes, that is, positively and seriously. This approach gives practical and effective results, creating all conditions and opportunities for women to live and work well. The law "On guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men", approved yesterday by the President, is an example of my opinion. And it shows that today the attention to women in our country has increased to higher heights than ever before.

This law guarantees equal participation of women and men in the management of public and state affairs, the electoral process, healthcare, education, science, culture, labor and social protection, as well as in other spheres of state and society life.

Such an opportunity, such attention, will certainly give every woman a cocktail, a desire to realize her abilities and abilities, work on new ideas, show initiative, as well as confidence in the future. New - leads to new achievements and goals. It encourages women to offer new approaches, new ideas and new initiatives.

The Law provides for the transfer of normative legal acts from gender legal expertise. If it is found that the normative legal document does not correspond to the printout of ensuring equal rights and opportunities for men and women, the conclusion of the gender legal expertise is sent for consideration to the body that adopted this normative legal act.

This document defines the powers of public administration bodies in the field of ensuring equal rights and opportunities for women and men individually. In addition, when promoting to senior positions of the state, the absence of discrimination on the basis of gender is guaranteed, a printout will be provided. Apparently, the preparation of women for leadership positions is one of the important tasks facing us, which also bears a special responsibility for the responsibility of political parties.

The Law defines the provision of equal rights and opportunities for women and men when political parties nominate candidates for the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan and deputies of local councils. We must ensure that women make up 50 percent of candidates for deputies in this year's elections.

It was also established that women and men have equal rights and opportunities in family relations and child rearing.

Equal rights and opportunities for men and women are ensured in labor relations.

Employers are prohibited from offering jobs only to representatives of the same sex, giving preference to one of the sexes, making different demands, demanding information from employers about their personal life, plans to become a child.

Chapter 7, article 32, regulates relations in the field of ensuring equal rights and opportunities for women and men through this law. It is very important that every woman learns to read, fully understands the rights and opportunities granted to her.

Because of these opportunities, we must take an active part in every process carried out in our country with a sense of responsibility. If a woman is active, the nation will be harmonious, the future of the nation is also in the hands of women. Therefore, we, women, must mobilize all the forces, knowledge and opportunities for the future of our nation and society.

After all, it is a woman who also maintains harmony in the family, stability in society, peace on earth, in a word, balance in the world.

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